

Analyst Administrator
Date Wednesday, January 5, 2022 3:57 PM

Sample Name	Description	Quality Checks
CAS113-6_1	Sample 021 By Administrator Date Wednesday, January 05 2022	The Quality Checks give rise to a Weak Bands warning for the sample.